

Self- Actualization of Deaf Workers in Culinary Industry

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Abstract:-The study intends to analyze the self-actualization of deaf employees in the culinary industry, specifically those working in Elait, Overdoughs, and Fruitas. By specifically evaluating the factors that affect their self-actualization, together with the barriers associated with the employment of employees with this type of disability, the proponents have sought to determine the extent in which these employees were to realize their potential in the industry. Many deaf workers have experience of being self reliant on their own since they do not want to be a bother to the normal community. A lot of deaf workers and individuals have depressing thoughts and anxiety since their disability was a bit of a hindrance since it can halt the progress on the premises. The proponents made use of a descriptive method to accurately gather sufficient data. A total of twenty-four (24) respondents participated in the study, whereby thirteen (13) of these were male and eleven (11) were female. Through the thorough analysis of the answered survey questionnaire, findings suggest that the deaf culture tend to be more academically smart as compared to those who do not have the disability as these individuals are more hardworking. At the same time, these same employees are more motivated when they are given recognition, whether big or small. This allows them to better recognize their self-worth and potential. However, it cannot be prevented that they are to feel an ounce of discomfort and self-doubt due to their disability. Henceforth, it is recommended by the researchers that these individuals are given equal treatment and proper acknowledgement as they are still capable of doing specific jobs despite their inability to hear.

Keywords:- *Self-Actualization, Deaf, Culinary Industry, Employees.*

INTRODUCTION

The biggest problem Deaf people were and still facing are negative perceptions about their capabilities and worth. Many skilled Deaf people face additional challenges with communication that many employers balk at addressing, when accommodations and solutions are readily available. An article on Upserve and Lightspeed explains what restaurants need to know about deaf employees (February 2018) was that there was nothing deaf employees can't do. They work and act the same inside the restaurant. There are other ways on deaf employees can work besides being on the front line. Most think being in the kitchen was less difficult for them since they only need their eyesight and their sense of touch. False, their visual and tactile sense increased by tenfold and has used that

advantage in the kitchen. Occupational difficulties of individuals who are Deaf include the inadequate understanding of employers regarding legal mandates and appropriate accommodations and poor academic preparation. With the current labor shortages going on in foodservice, reaching out to the disabled community is a win-win situation ; people wanting to work, and a foodservice operation finding latent talent. Additionally, those with disabilities have a level of grit and creativity they master to fit into a world that was not designed for them. Communication difficulties have been a significant contributor to poor employment rates and continue to be a primary barrier to job maintenance and advancement for the Deaf employee.

In the local setting, Deaf community in the Philippines are still having challenges when it comes to finding their way to be a part of any work force. Estiller-Corpuz (2016) administered a survey on the status of the deaf people in the Philippines. Many children were not able to go to school due to their parents being Deaf. Most Deaf are illiterate, not being able to read or write. This leads to a greater problem which is unemployment.

In the Philippines, the result of the 2010 Census of Population and Housing (CPH, 2010) shows that 1.443 million Filipinos or 1.57 percent, have a disability out of the household population of 92.1 million. (Silva-dela Cruz, F. &Calimpusan, E., 2018, p.1).

This encouraged the researchers to pursue this study as they found the importance of letting the hearing people be more aware that Deaf are struggling more than the normal workers who do not have any disabilities. Employment brings many benefits to the establishment as well as to the person and one is self-actualization. Self-actualization is the complete realization of one's potential and full development of one's abilities and appreciation for life. This concept is at the top of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. Hence, this study seeks to assess self-actualization of employed Deaf workers in three establishments employing Deaf.

According to Jeevan D'Souza, the word self-actualization has a wide variety of meanings depending on the situation at hand, but in a nutshell, it refers to achieving one's full potential. Self-actualization is synonymous with self-realization, self-empowerment, and self-reflection.

Communication with the Deaf or Hard of Hearing employees, whether just speaking with one of the Deaf employees, around the office or during a meeting, adapting to the way you speak and how you act in front of them.

Sadly, while much progress has been made to break down communication barriers in the workplace, there are still businesses and organizations that accommodations are not enough for their Deaf employees or customers and make themselves genuinely open and accessible to all.

Still there are many Deaf and Hard of Hearing people face unfair treatment at work or when trying to use services or information that only the hearing people can benefit from.

Better communication is the main solution for this. When we communicate, it helps develop stronger relationships with colleagues, leadership and management, customers, service users and other stakeholders.

If we know how to communicate properly, it helps to create a diverse and inclusive workplace culture that engages everyone because we understand each other's differences so that we can avoid discrimination.

Even in the modern times, still many companies don't prioritize or give importance in knowing how to properly handle Deaf or Hard of Hearing employees, and just expect them to do their job properly just like the hearing employees.

Having Deaf or Hard of Hearing employees, first is to be aware of their communication needs, so you can support them in the workplace.

Not meeting the expected adjustments for the Deaf employees is a common form of disability discrimination. Adjusting the regulations can include anything from audio equipment to BSL interpretation, translation and note-taking. If you have any additional equipment you need to purchase it can be funded through the Government's Access to Work scheme.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Generally, this study seeks to assess self-actualization of employed Deaf workers in three establishments employing Deaf.

This study aims to answer the following problems:

What is the demographic profile of the participants of the study in terms of:

- Age
- Gender
- Position
- Educational Attainment

What factors affect Self – Actualization on the Deaf employees in terms of?

Anti social on their peers, isolation, and being anxious on the premises.

Communication with the customers and the team members.

Overthinking about their disability that results in depression.

What are the barriers to employment of Deaf employees that have been encountered?

Did the Deaf employees attain Self-Actualization in their work experience?

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study is focused on the self-actualization of the Deaf workers in Elait, OverDoughs, and Fruitas.

Based on the research, the selected respondents determined the process of self-actualization based on their experience working on one of these establishments.

The conceptual model that was used in this research study was the input-output-process model where it shows the series of boxes that are connected to each other.

Fig. 1: IPO Model

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Maslow's hierarchy of needs is a motivational theory in psychology comprising a five-tier model of human needs, often depicted as hierarchical levels within a pyramid.

Fig. 2: Maslow Hierarchy of Needs

According to Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, esteem for oneself is about dignity, achievement, mastery, and independence.

Deaf workers want to improve themselves and to excel, which requires something they don't have. Second, they become anxious about what other people think about them. According to Maslow's, esteem needs the desire for reputation or respect from others. Deaf workers want to prove to others that their disabilities were not a hindrance to serving the customers.

Self-actualization was thought to be best conceptualized as the sum of its parts rather than as traits viewed in isolation. For example, a person who has a creative spirit, which was one trait of self-actualization, may still not be fully self-actualized. Some experts say the theory of self-actualization was more about how open a person was to growth and health rather than about achieving ideals such as perfection, success, or happiness. The process of self-actualization is different for everyone, and not all individuals achieve all levels of the hierarchy throughout their lives. While Maslow believed achieving self-actualization was somewhat rare and posited that only about 1% of the adult population has self-actualized, current research shows this number may be higher. Further, self-actualization has not been found to correlate with age, gender, income level, or race.

An article by D'Souza (2014) about the "SAGE Encyclopedia of Lifespan Human development about self-actualization" states that humans who self-actualize tend to be more selfless. As age comes, they tend to focus more on others' well-being rather than their own. They focus on others' happiness; they do not mind their own well-being because they tend to fix other people's problems. It has occurred that mentally healthy individuals pass through different stages of life and they intend to follow a path of growth that makes them less selfish and more selfless. When they tend to be selfless, they realize they have worth in being with others.

For most Deaf students in the Philippines, education stops at the secondary level. Few have attempted to be mainstream in higher education institutions, which lack the support systems for the Deaf (Salazar-Clemena, 2006).

According to Coconuts Manila (2018), a Filipino-owned ice cream store that embraces inclusivity with non-hearing employees (2018), Francis Reyes, CEO of the Caravan Food Group, Inc., told Coconuts Manila through a message on Facebook that the store opened its first branch in Century City in Makati City in April 2017. That Ice Cream store was called Elait. Elait was a play on words. Au lait is French for milk, and elated means to make someone happy, which essentially, was what they aim to give customers: milk and happiness. "Our team members are empowered through proper training on how to handle the shops by themselves. They gain confidence along the way knowing that they're truly capable individuals. It also helps that they do not feel alone since they work with many other members of the deaf community."

According to Reyes (2018), Overdoughs, another one of Caravan Food Group, Inc.'s concept stores, also has an employee with autism and will have part-timers with Down's syndrome.

The idea to employ deaf professionals actually came before Caravan. To find the right people, Reyes said he approached many foundations before finally finding the perfect partner: College of St. Benilde School of Deaf Education and Applied Studies (SDEAS). To further support the deaf community, Reyes initiated The Good Cookie Project under Overdoughs. A portion of the proceeds of their cookie sales funds the education of SDEAS' scholars.

(Tayao-Juego, 2019).

Dela Cruz and Calimpusan (2017) said Deaf employment in the Philippines still carries the discrimination of hiring disabled employees because they only rely on the physical appearance or the visible marks such as wheelchairs, white canes, and black eyeglasses to identify their needs. The reason was that there are no attendant and visible marks on their appearance such as wheelchairs, white canes, and black eyeglasses to identify their needs. The only time that they are recognized as Deaf is when they begin to talk using sign language. Looking at the bigger picture of the Deaf population in the Philippines, the opportunities remain to be limited for them. For more than ten years of the researcher's volunteer work with the Deaf community in the different parts of the country, it has been observed that the issues of equal access to economic opportunities such as employment have been prevalent among the Filipino Deaf nationwide.

Lester Yu, the founder and CEO of Fruititas Holdings Inc. (FHI), put an emphasis on bringing the qualified people on board from the beginning. Beyond that, he was committed to promoting fair employment opportunities by concentrating on people's abilities and the value they can add to the company. This included hiring deaf individuals to work as front-line personnel in the company's many food kiosks. Vangie Olivio, a Fruititas Ice Candy vendor in a Manila mall, expresses her joy at being able to serve clients on a daily basis. She previously worked in an office at a corporation, where she struggled to engage with others. She was lonely and bored of not being able to interact with her coworkers. Olivio discovered about FHI's "equalemployer" status in 2015 and applied. Despite the fact that she occasionally has problems with consumers, Olivio says that seeing happy clients makes her happy. FHI, as a firm formed by a Filipino, it placed Filipinos at the center of its operations. The food service company not only caters to the preferences of its customers, but it also gives back to society by being a good corporate citizen in key areas. According to Yu, as Fruititas Holdings Inc. grows, we don't lose sight of the necessity of giving back to society. We were proud to be one of the few organizations that employs people with disabilities (PWDs), since we believe that everyone can contribute value to the company. According to a study performed by the Institute for Labor Studies, the Department of Labor and Employment's (DOLE) policy research and advocacy arm, there is a huge need for businesses to be inclusive when it comes to hiring PWDs, particularly those with communication

challenges. Equal employment was not part of their business social obligation, it's part of their human resources strategy to avoid discrimination and offer all applicants a fair shot.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers utilized Descriptive Design, a type of Quantitative research method which should have comprehensible and accurate research questionnaires. In this research, it involved observing and describing the process of self-actualization of the Deaf workers.

The researchers used online survey questionnaires on Elait, Overdoughs, and Fruitas. For Elait, the branch in Metro Manila was Century City Mall. Furthermore, the researchers included the establishment with the same owner and mission but offer different products, such as Overdoughs. They have branches in Festival Supermall Alabang, Muntinlupa, Metro Manila. And lastly, the Fruitas Holdings, Inc. were also in Festival Supermall Alabang, Muntinlupa, Metro Manila. The researchers have discovered that they also recognize deaf people and other persons with disabilities by hiring them as their employees in food stalls as well. The population of this study targets the deaf workers of Elait.

Overdoughs and Elait have the same owner except Fruitas but the three participating establishments have the same goal. Their mission was to prove that the deaf workers were not so different from the hearing workers. The 3 establishments were proving that they work the same way as the hearing employee's work. They were only missing their hearing sense but they work twice as fast as their counterparts.

Elait was a Thai idea that combines a rolled ice cream and yogurt. Elait (e-late) was a play on words that combines the French term for milk, "Lait," and "Elate," which means "ecstatically pleased." Elait's objective was to spread happiness and positivity through their products because people can't really be sad when they consume ice cream. The researchers chose to write and share about the Elait experience not only because they provide excellent ingredients in their made-to-order rolled ice cream, but also because it's admirable what they do for the deaf brothers and sisters who have been granted job chances.

The participants of this research were the deaf individuals who were working in Metro Manila, specifically those two branches were working in a fast pace and experiencing discrimination on their workplace.

DATA GATHERING AND ANALYSIS

This research was conducted through online Google forms. The proponents have decided that the respondents for the study would be the previous workers of the food and drink establishments who were contacted through the official Facebook page and message through SMS text of the

establishment's employees and will be given the online survey forms for them to answer. The proponents used an online survey and Google Forms as a platform that contained all the survey forms and responses from all respondents since the scope of the study fell during this time of pandemic. 4-point Likert scale were used in the questionnaire since it also offers collection of data which is organized into a scaled hierarchy. Consider the 4-point Likert Scale in the study because it gives the assumption on the "survey of opinions" in which the key assumption would be present in getting the needed data from the guest, according to the study of Joshi (2015). Hence, this concept gives the topic a more distinct and explanatory and it helps the aim of researchers to measure their proposed topic. Once all responses are gathered, the researchers analyzed the data using Pearson Correlation Coefficient to test whether the factors (quality of post, user experiences and people reached) have a significant relationship with the effectiveness of social media. The Pearson correlation coefficient is a test statistic that measures the relationship among two continuous variables. It aims to measure the strength of the association between the variables and map out the direction of their relationship (Pearson's Correlation Coefficient 2020). The range of the results will vary from -1, having Perfect Negative Correlation, to +1, having Perfect Positive Correlation (Pearson Product-Moment Correlation 2018).

Mainly 24 who fit within this research's required criteria. The researchers of this study used the simple form of online questionnaire as this study's quantitative data analysis method, using Google Forms. The questionnaires will showcase questions about Self-Actualization, where did they first work, how is their experience working at their designated workplace, why did they take the job opportunity, how do they feel towards hearing people especially customers and such. The prior respondents would be the deaf workers of Elait, OverDoughs and Fruitas due to the researchers' gathering of effective information and data if the actual people with disabilities would be answering the questions. Online survey questionnaires were used as the data gathering instrument for this study. It is also the most convenient way to collect data coming from a deaf person. Survey questionnaires are used to gather data by the number of respondents. The researchers used a purposive sampling method to rely on the data they have collected from the population members. The researchers contacted the potential respondents and asked them if they were willing to be part of the researcher's study. The purpose of this is to have the respondents affected by the topic. It is to show how freely and relying on legitimate opinions of people regarding on their experience as a deaf worker or encountering with deaf people. Since the research is optimized on surveys, it is the best approach for this study. The data gathered showed how they are coping with their struggles with work, customers, and their self-actualization about themselves, their situation and how they live their lives. Also, the data showed why they took the opportunity to work on kiosks. How reliable and reachable it is for the potential customers and even supporters of the deaf community. The researchers used methodological triangulation to use several methods to gather reliable data. They merely observe the answers on the questionnaire. Thus, the researchers asked permission from

three (3) establishments, Elait, Overdoughs, and Fruitas to permit the researchers to conduct their data gathering. The researchers used Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs as reference to understand the Self-Actualization of the deaf workers in their day-to-day actions, how they handled their hardships and misunderstandings and how to accept themselves.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researchers have gathered data from 24 respondents and have provided a clear outcome that answers the statement of the problem that offered a viewpoint on how the demographics respond towards the set of questions.

Demographics

Age	Frequency	Percent
25 years and below	12	50.0
26 - 30 years old	3	12.5
31 - 35 years old	6	25.0
36 - 40 years old	1	4.2
41 - 45 years old	2	8.3
Total	24	100.0

Table 1: Age

Table 1 reveals that among the 24 respondents the researchers gathered, 25 years old and below ones who are usually working at their establishments with a frequency of 12 and 50%. The group with the lowest percentage of 4.2% are the 36-40 years old with a frequency of 1. In accordance with the Department of Labor and Employment (2017), it is unlawful for an employer to deny any employee’s or worker’s promotion or opportunity for training because of age; forcibly lay off an employee or worker because of old age; or impose early retirement on the basis of such employee’s or worker’s age.

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	11	45.8
Male	13	54.2
Total	24	100.0

Table 2 : Gender

Table 2 represents the demographic representation of respondents. With a total of 24, and with the classification of the highest percentage are the Male with a frequency of 13 and a percentage of 54.2%. While noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) occurs in both men and women, men are nearly 3 times more likely to develop it. Hearing loss in men is more

prevalent because they are typically the ones who are working in loud environments (Miracle Ear, 2021). In a study by Gallinger (2016), he explained that deaf males in particular hold more conservative views and tend to work harder than women in their youthful days; they tend to be more recognized by the hearing community and offer more and more work to them.

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
College	15	62.5
High School	7	29.2
Others	2	8.3
Total	24	100.0

Table 3: Educational Attainment

Table 3 reveals the educational attainment of the respondents in which the respondents in the college level have the highest percentage of 62.5% and a frequency of 15. While the rest of the respondents are High school graduates with a percentage of 29.2% and a frequency of 7. The lowest rank was the other educational attainment which was not mentioned with a 2%, which means that they are either an undergraduate or having a low educational background. Educational level is a key factor in understanding the employment status of adults with hearing loss (National Research Council, 2005). Beatty (2019) explained in her study the educational disparities between hearing and non-hearing students are evident in delays in literacy among deaf students. Deaf students are having difficulty finishing school tasks due to the old ways of using communication in the classroom by using oral communication like vocal instead of sign language even when there were deaf children involved.

Course	Frequency	Percent
Architecture	1	4.2
Bachelor in Applied Deaf Studies	3	12.5
BIT	1	4.2
BS chemical Engineering	1	4.2
BSRT	1	4.2
Business Operations Management	1	4.2
Hospitality Management	6	25.0
HUMSS	2	8.3
Multimedia arts	2	8.3
N/A	6	25.0
Total	24	100

Table 4: Course

Table 4 shows the course that the respondents took in college. Results showed that the majority of the respondents with a frequency of 6 and a percentage of 25% study in Hospitality Management. In a meeting of UEDF (March 2017)

barista skills are in great demand in the hospitality industry and the development of barista skills courses for deaf students would pave a way for people with hearing impairment to venture into the industry. The highest frequency of 6 as well as 25% of the respondents did not finish their education in the past. The lowest results of the respondents on their course decisions are Architecture, BIT, BS chemical engineering and BSRT with all of the frequency being 1 and percentage of 4.2%.

What are the factors affecting Self-Actualization on the Deaf employees?

1.00-1.49	Strongly Agree/Very Low
1.50-2.49	Agree/Low
2.50-3.49	Disagree/High
3.50-4.00	Strongly Disagree / Very High

Table 5: Verbal interpretation of the Mean

Mental health generated a mean of 3.08 with verbal interpretation of high.

Chron articles on deaf challenges in the hearing workplace(April 20, 2021) deafness and hearing loss poses challenges both the workers with the impairments and their employees. Many deaf workers themselves are having the fear of doubt and having depression due to their own hearing impairment. Such as deaf employees being judged by not using their ASL correctly. In order for the deaf workers to be more comfortable on the premises is to be not be afraid of making a mistake in-front of their co-workers. Deaf workers themselves need support emotionally and physically on their daily tasks. Even more so on a ASL workplace, but if a deaf employee is on a unsupportive environment, they may shut down emotionally and begin to look for other job opportunities

Communication	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Communication is a barrier between the customer and the deaf employee	3.1 7	Disagree
Struggles on vocal communication	3.1 7	Disagree
Sign language helps in communicating	3.4 6	Disagree
Sign language aids are evident in the workplace	3.4 2	Disagree
Overall Assessment of Communication	3.3 0	High

Table 7: Communication

The table shows that the highest rank that resulted a mean of 3.46 with a verbal interpretation of disagree where the respondents of the use of sign language on communicating with their team and their clients, while the two questions of having the lowest rank of having a mean of 3.17 with a verbal interpretation of disagree is that communication is a barrier between the customer and the employee and having struggles on using vocal/verbal communication whenever they had to use to communicate with others. In overall, the Communication garnered a mean of 3.30 with a verbal interpretation of high.

Stoker and Orwat(2018) stated deaf employees and regular workers have massive communication barriers due to having difficulty communicating because one of the party is not knowledgeable on how to deal with the hearing impaired which has caused a commotion in the workplace. Communication challenges were present withingroup interactions causing the deaf workers to guess what was being said. Research showed that the preferred mode of communication was the ASL(American Sign Language) and written communication instead.

Experience in the Workplace	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Educational background helps in work know-how	3.08	Disagree

Mental Health	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Struggles to work on a fast-paced service.	2.96	Disagree
Having doubts and fears when applying for a job.	3.08	Disagree
Having worries about the current job.	2.58	Disagree
Discrimination bothers you	3.08	Disagree
Accepting of disability relieves you from worrying	3.29	Disagree
Recognition motivates you to work harder	3.50	Strongly Disagree
Overall Assessment of mental health	3.08	High

Table 6: Mental Health

Table 6 shows that the highest rank that resulted in a mean of 3.50 wherein the respondents strongly agree that having recognition motivates them to work harder to give them more confidence on completing tasks. This is because employee recognition is a method of support that helps employees know their contributions are recognized and appreciated. Employees want to know how they are doing, and recognizing employees demonstrates what success looks like (Hastwell, 2020). Meanwhile, the lowest rank accumulated a mean of 2.58 whereas the respondents agreed on having doubts and fears when applying for the job. Overall, the

Team mates are accommodating	21	3.	Disagree
Recruitment process is difficult	00	3.	Disagree
Information at work is not accessible	42	2.	Agree
Overall Assessment of Experience in the Workplace	6771	2.	High

Table 8: Experience in the workplace

Table 8 represents the experiences of the employees in the workplace. Results show that the highest rank resulted in a mean of 3.21 with a verbal interpretation of disagreement wherein the respondent’s teammates are accommodated in the workplace for greater synchronization. The lowest rank accumulated a mean of 2.42 with a verbal interpretation of agreement whereas the respondents agree on having doubts and fears when applying for the job. Many companies are wary of hiring deaf job candidates. Deaf candidates are often perceived as too “disabled” to work at their companies, or that they will cause an undue burden on the business due to a need for accommodations (Deaf Job Wizard, 2019). Overall, the experiences in the workplace generated a mean of 2.6771 with verbal interpretation of high.

Limited hearing hinders the interactions in the workplace and with the customers.	13	3.	Disagree
Inconsistent expectation of employer	63	2.	Disagree
Unrealistic expectations of employer	54	2.	Disagree
No interpreters available	63	2.	Disagree
Overall Assessment of BARRIERS TO EMPLOYMENT OF DEAF EMPLOYEE THAT HAVE BEEN ENCOUNTERED	635417	2.	High

Table 9: Barriers to Employment Encountered

Table 9 represents the barriers to employment encountered. Results show that the highest rank that resulted in a mean of 3.13 with a verbal interpretation of disagreement wherein the respondents have limited hearing hinders the interaction in the workplace and they have PWD ID’s that are acknowledged when using public transportation. An individual with hearing impairment, the most obvious communication problem in the workplace is the presence of background noise. Noise is highly prevalent in industrial settings and, among workers with noise-induced hearing loss, noise is mentioned most frequently as an obstacle and a source of annoyance in the workplace (Hetu, 1994). The lowest rank accumulated a mean of 2.42 with a verbal interpretation of low whereas the overtime payment has not been fulfilled properly. Overall, barriers to employment encountered generated a mean of 2.635417 with verbal interpretation of high.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results the researchers gathered, the following conclusions were given:

The researchers have formally concluded that the deaf employees are able to achieve self-actualization when customers are able to acknowledge their effort and hardwork. At the same time, these same individuals tend to be more motivated when they receive recognition, whether big or small. To be recognized by the public allows them to feel a sense of hope and realize their self-worth. Although, it cannot be prevented that they encounter a feeling of self-doubt and discomfort when dealing with other people due to their inability to hear. With this, it is evident that one of the barriers that hinder them from being able to perform well in their jobs is the fast-paced environment that they are required to keep up with. At the same time, these employees are having a hard time finding the right occupation as there are times where they are not able to meet the employer’s expectations, thus, making the recruitment process difficult for them. Another barrier that they experience is discrimination, as some people in the society tend to not understand the hardship of these individuals. Oftentimes, deaf people are required to show their PWD IDs in order to be acknowledged as a Person with Disability (PWD). Henceforth, in order to overcome these challenges, clear communication should be a priority in their

What are the barriers to employment of Deaf employees that have been encountered?

BARRIERS TO EMPLOYMENT ENCOUNTERED	Mean	M	Verbal Interpretation
Communication difficulties	96	2.	Disagree
Low morale in the workplace	46	2.	Agree
Conflicts related to deaf culture	88	2.	Disagree
Education level was not met in past job employments	50	2.	Disagree
Misunderstanding in meetings	79	2.	Disagree
Facing discrimination during work hours	83	2.	Disagree
Acknowledgement of PWD IDs in public transportation	13	3.	Disagree
Overtime payment has not been fulfilled properly	42	2.	Agree

workplace as this is primarily the key to having a successful role in everyday life. In today's culture, individuals with a certain type of disability should be given equal treatment as their specific disabilities is not enough of a reason to hinder them from performing well on their day-to-day tasks, as these people tend to be more academically smart, as compared to their counterparts.

RECOMMENDATION

As to the Establishments:

It is recommended that the managers should be more physically present whenever their employee is having trouble on their self-worth

It is recommended that the other workers accommodate their deaf co-workers properly

It is recommended that the establishment add signage posters for awareness with regard to the deaf employees in order to reduce the risk of encountering issues.

It is recommended that the management include deaf and PWD-friendly devices and equipment in every establishment that people can go to.

It is recommended that establishments promote and normalize recruiting persons with disabilities (PWD).

It is recommended that the establishment conduct employee training to assist the concerns of the employees.

It is recommended that the establishment conduct occasional team building to make the employees feel more comfortable and be at ease with the environment.

It is recommended that the establishment showcase the recruitment of PWDs through social media platforms to encourage other establishments to do the same as well.

It is recommended that the establishment prioritize getting feedback from its customers in order to understand the perception of the customer and how they can better improve their services.

As to the Deaf Employees:

It is recommended that they alert their managers immediately in cases they are having a hard time understanding the order of the customer.

It is recommended that they maintain proper attitude and conduct at all times, especially in cases where the customer is complaining in order to reduce the likelihood of making the issue worse.

It is recommended that they attend employee training and team building to make them feel more at ease.

It is recommended that they build strong bonds with their co-workers to motivate them to do better in the workplace.

As to the Future Researchers:

It is recommended that they understand Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs before starting any research related to the deaf culture.

It is recommended that they further understand deaf culture

It is recommended that they show more appreciation and have significant knowledge in using FSL.

It is recommended that the researchers think and apply relevant topics in their study to help future researchers as well that are interested in creating related studies.

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